

**MATHEMATICAL MODELING METHODS FOR
IMPROVING ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY IN REPAIR
PRODUCTION****B.A.Kholkhojaev**

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ABSTRACT

The article presents mathematical models that optimize structural and technological solutions in repair production. The proposed mathematical model will increase the economic efficiency of aircraft repair.

Main Part:

In the process of improving management and planning in repair production, economic and mathematical models and methods acquire great importance, as they make it possible to select the best solution among many possible options according to specified criteria [6].

Optimization primarily serves the purpose of selecting those solutions that ensure maximum economic efficiency. Economic efficiency is characterized by the relationship between the amount of scarce resources used in the repair process. This relationship can be expressed using a function.

$$Z = f(x), \quad x \in X.$$

A smaller volume of aircraft (AC) repairs with a given amount of expenditure leads to a decrease in efficiency.

A larger volume of aircraft repairs with the same amount of expenditure indicates an increase in efficiency. [2]

Every enterprise, in its decisions regarding the optimal use of resources, strives to maximize profit. The profit of an enterprise is a function of these variables.

$\varphi_i(\chi_1, \chi_2, \chi_3, \dots, \chi_n)$ of these variables. Let us assume that the enterprise has reserves of resources of the i -th type with a volume of b_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$). Since the enterprise requires production that ensures maximum profit while using only the available resources, the optimization problem consists in finding such $\chi_1, \chi_2, \chi_3, \dots, \chi_n$ values at which

$$f(\chi_1, \chi_2, \chi_3, \dots, \chi_n) \rightarrow \max \quad (1)$$

$$\varphi_i(\chi_1, \chi_2, \chi_3, \dots, \chi_n) \leq b_i \quad (i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m) \quad (2)$$

$$\chi_j \geq 0 \quad (j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n) \quad (3)$$

If the problem uses the criterion of minimizing costs under the condition of fulfilling the contract, then the objective function $f(\chi_1, \chi_2, \chi_3, \dots, \chi_n)$ will represent the costs, while the constraints $\varphi_i(\chi_1, \chi_2, \chi_3, \dots, \chi_n) \leq b_i$ - the conditions for fulfilling the contract for the production of goods of type ($j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$). It is necessary to find such values $\chi_1, \chi_2, \chi_3, \dots, \chi_n$, at which.

$$f(\chi_1, \chi_2, \chi_3, \dots, \chi_n) \rightarrow \min \quad (4)$$

$$\varphi_i(\chi_1, \chi_2, \chi_3, \dots, \chi_n) \leq b_i \quad (i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m) \quad (5)$$

$$\chi_j \geq 0 \quad (j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n) \quad (6)$$

As is well known, there are various structural and technological solutions that are multifactorial. [3]

In this study, we develop a stochastic mathematical model of the technological process for repairing aircraft units.

To do this, we denote the influencing factors of the technological process of aircraft unit repair by the variables χ_j , where j is the index number of the variable. ($j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k$), a t — the index number of the observation. Structural and technological solutions are denoted by Y_i , where $t = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$

It is necessary to distinguish the degree of dependence of the independent variables in the model, which is represented by statistical parameters. B_j ,

$$j = (1, 2, 3, \dots, k.)$$

Within the framework of this analysis, it is possible to take the intersection point of the variable χ_1 which considers a single value $\chi_{1t} = 1$ for all t . If this is true, then β_1 it represents the point of intersection of the function with the ordinate axis, and the linear mathematical model with variables is written as

$$Y_t = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \chi_{2t} + \beta_3 \chi_{3t} + \dots + \beta_k \chi_{kt} + U_t, \quad (t = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n) \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) appears rather complex; however, it can be examined in detail for the case with two variables.

To determine the meaning of the model parameters, we will temporarily disregard the presence of errors in the equation and consider only the linear dependence of the variables.

t	y_t	χ_{2t}	χ_{3t}
1	10	10	12
2	13	8	14
3	15	6	18
4	20	5	30
5	18	3	25
$n=5$	$y_i=76$	$\chi_{2t}=32$	$\chi_{3t}=99$

Let us consider the case of the technological solution function.

The structural and technological solution (TS) depends on the number of workers (NW), the type of tools (TT), the fixtures (F), and the materials (M).

Then, the mathematical model takes the following form:

$$Y_t = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \chi_{2t} + \beta_3 \chi_{3t} + \dots + \beta_k \chi_{kt}; \quad (2)$$

If we introduce the following designations:

$$y_i = TP, \quad \chi_{2t} = KP, \quad \chi_{3t} = BI, \quad \chi_{4t} = IIP, \quad \chi_{5t} = M,$$

then we obtain the following function: $Y_i = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \chi_{2t} + \beta_3 \chi_{3t} + \beta_4 \chi_{4t} + \beta_5 \chi_{5t}$

$$TP = \beta_1 + \beta_2 KP + \beta_3 BI + \beta_4 IIP + \beta_5 M; \quad (3)$$

The estimated parameters for the model with quantitative variables can be obtained using the least squares method, and finding the sum of squared deviations is reduced to solving a system of linear equations with unknowns.

The system of equations appears rather complex, and the task is reduced to determining

$$\begin{aligned} & \beta_1 n + \beta_2 \chi_{2t} + \beta_3 \chi_{3t} + \dots + \beta_k \chi_{kt} = Y_i \\ \text{the unknown parameters: } & \beta_1 \chi_{2t} + \beta_2 \chi_{2t}^2 + \beta_3 \chi_{2t} \chi_{3t} + \dots + \beta_k \chi_{2t} \chi_{kt} = \chi_{2t} Y_i; \\ & \beta_1 \chi_{kt} + \beta_2 \chi_{kt} \chi_{2t} + \beta_3 \chi_{kt} \chi_{3t} + \dots + \beta_k \chi_{kt}^2 = \chi_{kt} Y_i. \end{aligned}$$

(4)

The procedure for calculating the parameters of independent variables using a specific example.

Let us assume that it is necessary to calculate the parameters β_1 , β_2 , β_3 in the mode

$$Y_i = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \chi_{2t} + \beta_3 \chi_{3t} + U_i; \quad (5)$$

in the presence of observed values Y , χ_2 , χ_3 .

In this case, system (4) takes the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \beta_1 n + \beta_2 \chi_{2t} + \beta_3 \chi_{3t} &= Y_i \\
 \beta_1 \chi_{2t} + \beta_2 \chi_{2t}^2 + \beta_3 \chi_{2t} \chi_{3t} &= \chi_{2t} Y_i \\
 \beta_1 \chi_{3t} + \beta_2 \chi_{3t} \chi_{2t} + \beta_3 \chi_{3t}^2 &= \chi_{3t} Y_i
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

The given system of linear equations can be solved using the Gaussian elimination method. To do this, the first equation is multiplied by 6.4, and the resulting expression is subtracted from the second equation, thereby eliminating the first variable from the second equation.

The resulting mathematical model with three variables makes it possible to select appropriate design and technological solutions for repair processes independently of the number of workers and the type of tools used.

In a similar way, a mathematical model can be obtained for selecting the technological processes of aircraft component repair regardless of the desired influencing factors.

Thus, increasing repair efficiency according to this criterion defines and accelerates the process of finding the optimal option for aircraft structure repair

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